

**PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS FOR FORMING STUDENTS' COMPETENCE FOR
IN SUBORDINATION AGAINST CORRUPTION****Akhmedova Dilnora Kobilzhonovna**

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Abstract.

This article analyzes the pedagogical conditions for developing anti-corruption resistance competence among university students. The study highlights the importance of fostering an active civic position, legal culture, moral and ethical values, and commitment to the principles of academic integrity in combating corruption. Based on the research findings, effective pedagogical factors and practical recommendations for developing students' anti-corruption resistance competence have been identified.

Keywords: corruption, anti-corruption resistance competence, university students, pedagogical conditions, academic integrity, legal culture, civic position, anti-corruption culture.

In today's context of globalization and digital transformation, corruption is considered one of the most pressing problems negatively impacting the development of society. The prevention of corruption is carried out not only through legal mechanisms but also through educational processes. Especially among students studying in higher educational institutions, the formation of an intolerant attitude toward corruption and the competence of disobedience is one of the important tasks facing the state and society. The competence of disobedience is understood as an individual's ability to consciously resist corrupt situations such as illegal interest, bribery, connections, and conflicts of interest, to reject them, and to be able to report such cases in the appropriate manner.

The formation of students' competence in non-compliance with corruption is a multi-factor pedagogical process that requires the presence of a number of conditions.

First, it is necessary to enrich the content of anti-corruption education in higher educational institutions. Incorporating topics on academic integrity, legal literacy, the socio-economic consequences of corruption, and international anti-corruption experience into the curricula will expand students' knowledge and worldview. This knowledge fosters critical thinking and a conscious attitude toward corruption in students. Secondly, the use of interactive methods in the educational process is of great importance. Methods of discussion, debate, case study, role-playing games, and problem situation analysis develop students' skills in making

correct decisions in corruption situations. Such methods allow for the combination of theoretical knowledge with practical experience. Third, it is necessary to create an environment of academic integrity. A firm attitude must be formed among students toward instances of plagiarism, forgery, and unfairness in receiving and evaluating illegal assistance. Adherence to the principles of academic integrity creates a strong anti-corruption stance in future professional activities. Fourth, the development of students' civic engagement is an important pedagogical factor. Involving young people in social projects, volunteer activities, and public oversight activities strengthens their sense of responsibility for the development of society.

As a result, they are formed as active citizens who are not indifferent to corruption. Fifth, the effective use of digital technologies serves to develop the competence of non-compliance. Electronic educational platforms, online seminars, digital propaganda tools, and anti-corruption mobile applications serve as effective tools for increasing the legal and moral knowledge of young people.

The competence of non-compliance with corruption in students consists of the following components: legal knowledge; moral values; critical thinking; civic responsibility; skills in identifying and evaluating corruption situations; and the ability to resist illegal actions.

Nowadays, social networks such as Instagram, Telegram, Facebook, YouTube and TikTok have become an important source of information in the daily life of young people. In particular, Instagram has a great influence on the formation of the worldview, values and civic position of students. Therefore, this platform can be effectively used in the development of anti-corruption culture and the formation of non-compliance competence.

The organization of short videos (Reels), infographics, posts, and live broadcasts on the negative consequences of corruption, its harm to the development of society, and the importance of honesty and justice through Instagram enriches students' knowledge on this issue. The rapid dissemination of visual information serves to attract the attention of young people and foster an intolerant attitude toward corruption. Furthermore, the pages of anti-corruption specialists, educators, bloggers, and public figures serve as an important spiritual and educational resource for students. Their speeches on honesty, legality, and civic responsibility inspire young people to stand up to corruption. Through Instagram's interactive features - surveys, Q&A, comments, and discussions - students have the opportunity to express their opinions on corruption-related issues, participate in debates, and develop critical thinking skills. This strengthens their competence in correctly assessing corruption situations and taking a firm position on them. In addition, the organization of anti-corruption actions, competitions, flash

mobs and social projects through social networks increases the activity of students in this process. As a result, young people develop civic responsibility, social activity, and the competence of non-compliance with corruption. Thus, Instagram and other social networks are an innovative pedagogical tool for forming the competence of non-compliance with corruption in students, playing an important role in increasing their legal culture, strengthening anti-corruption immunity, and developing an active civic position.

In education. Implementation of student admission, evaluation, and diploma issuance processes in higher educational institutions through electronic platforms. Reduction of the human factor as a result of the implementation of electronic journal and electronic dean's office systems. Establishment of monitoring for plagiarism and academic integrity using artificial intelligence. Development of online systems for receiving and reviewing student applications. Public administration. Expansion of access to most public services in online form. Improvement of electronic document management and digital identification systems. Expanding the practice of analyzing and monitoring citizens' appeals using artificial intelligence. In the banking and financial sector. Increasing the volume of services provided through digital banks and mobile applications. Widespread implementation of QR codes, biometric identification, and remote payment systems. Development of digital monitoring systems that ensure the transparency of financial transactions. In the healthcare sector. Widespread use of electronic medical cards and electronic prescription systems. Development of telemedicine services. Expanding the practice of diagnostics and medical data analysis based on artificial intelligence. In the fight against corruption, conducting public procurement and tender processes entirely on electronic platforms. Monitoring the expenditure of budget funds through open databases. Development of electronic queues, electronic appeals, and electronic control systems. Implementation of systems for identifying and analyzing corruption risks based on artificial intelligence. In the field of social networks and media. Ensuring the openness of government agencies' activities through Instagram, Telegram, and YouTube platforms. Expanding the ability of citizens to promptly report cases of corruption. Strengthening legal and anti-corruption advocacy through digital media. "The acceleration of digitalization processes, along with reducing corruption factors, is becoming an effective pedagogical tool for forming students' competence in non-compliance with corruption." Because digital systems strengthen the principles of transparency, openness and accountability, and strengthen the values of honesty and legality among young people.

The article proposes to integrate the content of anti-corruption education with the concept of non-compliance competence. Additionally, pedagogical conditions aimed at developing students' skills in identifying, evaluating, and countering corrupt situations have been systematized.

Conclusion: The formation of students' competence in non-compliance with corruption is one of the important pedagogical directions for corruption prevention. The effectiveness of this process is directly linked to improving the content of anti-corruption education, creating an environment of academic integrity, using interactive pedagogical technologies, and increasing students' civic engagement. The implementation of these pedagogical conditions into practice serves to form a firm position of young people against corruption.

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